

Synthesis, Spectra and Physiological Activity of 8H-Pyrano (3,2-f) Benzoxazole-8-Ones

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A few 2-aryl and 2-heterocyclic substituted (3,2-f) benzoxazoles have been synthesised by condensing 6-amino-8-bromo-7-hydroxy-2-methyl chromone with aromatic and heterocyclic carboxylic acids employing polyphosphoric acid as cyclodehydrating agent. The Ultraviolet, Infrared, N. M. R. and Mass spectra of these compounds have been presented. A study of antibacterial and antifungal activities of these compounds has revealed that 2-*p*-toluyl, 2-*o*-toluyl, 2-(2-naphthyl) and 2-(3-pyridyl)-8H-pyrano (3,2-f) benzoxazoles-8-ones possess moderate antifungal activity at 100 p.p.m. dilution.

CHROMONE derivatives containing a furan or a pyran system fused to the benzene ring have been reported to possess pharmacological properties¹. In the previous communications from these laboratories²⁻⁴, the synthesis of a few chromono (7,8) and (6,7) oxazoles has been carried out with the purpose of elucidating their physiological activity. In our earlier communication⁴ polyphosphoric acid has been used as a dehydrative cyclising agent for the preparation of oxazoles. Encouraged by the results and yields, it was extended to the synthesis of 8H-pyrano (3,2-f) benzoxazole-8-ones, using easily accessible naphthoic and heterocyclic carboxylic acids. The present work describes the results of these investigations.

For the purpose of synthesising the title compounds 6-amino-8-bromo-7-hydroxy-2-methyl chromone⁵(I) has been condensed with aromatic and heterocyclic carboxylic acids using polyphosphoric acid as a dehydrative cyclising agent to yield the corresponding oxazole(II) (Chart I). These acids made use of in the condensation include *o*- and *p*-toluic acids, α - and β -naphthoic acids, *o*-chlorobenzoic acid, coumarin-3-carboxylic acid and its 6-bromo analogue and pyridine-3-carboxylic acid (or nicotinic acid). The yields in all the above cases have been nearly quantitative except in the cases of nicotinic acid and *o*-chlorobenzoic acid. The aldehydes corresponding to the acids utilised are fairly difficult to make and as such this method of using polyphosphoric acid is of great utility for making pyrano benzoxazoles in such cases. The temperature employed and the duration of the reaction varied with the acid employed (for details see experimental section). The resulting 8H-pyrano (3,2-f) benzoxazole-8-ones [more commonly termed as chromono (6,7) oxazoles] have been included in Table 2.

Spectral Characteristics of pyrano (3,2-f) benzoxazoles. Ultraviolet Spectra :

All the title compounds exhibited three main regions of absorption around 229 ± 12 nm, 275 ± 15 nm, and 345 ± 12 nm. The former two are attributed to chromophores (a) and (b) respectively. The third is assignable to the extended conjugated system (c). (Chart II)

However, the higher wavelength band has been found to be split into two clear maxima (around 310 ± 15 nm and 345 ± 12 nm), most probably due to the effect of the bromine atom on the chromophore (C¹).

In the case of 2-(3-coumarinyl) derivatives a band around 355 nm has been observed for the cinnamoyl chromophore of the coumarin moiety. 2-(3-coumarinyl) derivatives exhibit a high degree of fluorescence. 2-(3-coumarinyl) derivative gave a band at 457 nm (light violet fluorescence) and 2-(6-bromo-3-coumarinyl) derivative gave a band at 464 nm (yellow fluorescence).

Infrared Spectra :

The I.R. spectra are similar to the (2,3-e) series of pyrano-benzoxazoles⁴. However, the chromone

Chart - II

(2) 2-*o*-TOLUYL-8H-PYRANO BENZOXAZOLE-8-ONE

δ -values	No. of protons	Assignment
2.5 (d) ($J=1$ CPS)	3	6-Methyl (long range coupling).
2.9 (s)	3	Aromatic side chain methyl.
6.22 (q) ($J=1$ CPS)	1	7-Proton (vinyl).
7.3-7.5 (m)	4	Aromatic protons of side phenyl.
8.5 (s)	1	9-Proton.

s=singlet; d=doublet; m=multiplet; q=quartet.

The points of interest in these N.M.R. spectra are (i) the appearance of the signal for the 6-Me protons at 2.5 δ , precisely at the same value where the 8-Me of oxazolo (7, 8) chromone⁴ revealed its signal indicating that the linear or angular fusion does not affect the environment around this chromone methyl and (ii) the 9-proton signal around 8.2 δ appearing as a singlet, which confirms the linear fusion of the oxazole with the chromone system. In addition, with the 2-*o*-toluy analogue, the methyl protons of this substituent were found to undergo a downward shift owing to the deshielding effect of the oxazole C=N while, with the corresponding *p*-toluy derivative these protons appeared at 2.43 δ due to the absence of such effect.

carbonyl frequencies have been found to be shifted to lower wavelenghts (1630-1640 cm^{-1}), possibly due to the planarity of the (3, 2-f) system being greater than the (2, 3-e) analogues.

N.M.R. Spectra :

The N.M.R. spectra were recorded on a Varian A-60 N.M.R. spectrometer in duterated chloroform. The results have been included in Table 1.

Mass Spectra :

The mass spectra were recorded on a RMU-6L Mass Spectrometer with inlet temperatures ranging from 150-200° and an electron beam energy of 70 ev.

TABLE 1—(1) 2-*p*-TOLUYL-8H-PYRANO BENZOXAZOLE-8-ONE

δ -values	No. of protons	Assignment
2.5 (d) ($J=1$ CPS)	3	6-Methyl (long range coupling).
2.43 (s)	3	Aromatic methyl.
6.19 (q) ($J=1$ CPS)	1	7-Proton (vinyl).
7.25-7.4 (m)	4	Aromatic protons of side phenyl.
8.2 (s)	1	9-Proton. It has come in low field because it is flanked by carbonyl oxygen and oxazole nitrogen.

The mass spectra of two pyrano (3, 2-f) benzoxazoles, viz. 4-bromo-6-methyl-2-*o*-toluy-8H-pyrano (3, 2-f) benzoxazole-8-one (No.1) and its 2-(2-naphthyl) analogue (No. 2), have been recorded. The fragmentation pattern is included in Chart 3. The molecular ion intensities observed indicate that the (3, 2-f) system is less stable to electron impact than the (2,3-e) system⁴ in which case the molecular ions are the base peaks.

Owing to the presence of the 4-bromine, loss of bromine from the molecular ion was found to be a competing process with the retro-Diels-Alder fission of the pyrone moiety. Moreover, the fragment obtained by this Diels-Alder fission was found to undergo a concerted loss of three molecules of carbon monoxide. The base peaks in the spectra were found to depend on the nature of the 2-substituent. Thus, while the nitrile radical ion was the base peak in the case of the 2-naphthyl derivative, an

oxygenated fragment was the base peak with the 2-*o*-toluyl analogue. The fragmentation pattern is indicated in the scheme below.

Aspergillus niger and *Trichophyton semii*. 2-*p*-Toluy, 2-*o*-toluyl, 2-(2-naphthyl) and 2-(3-pyridyl)-8H-pyrano (3, 2-f) benzoxazole-8-ones are found to be moderately active at 100 p.p.m. dilution.

Experimental

Preparation of 8H-pyrano (3,2-f) benzoxazole-8-ones :

Polyphosphoric acid was prepared by stirring a mixture of phosphorous pentoxide (15 g) and ortho-phosphoric acid (10 ml) at 100° for 1 hour. Then a mixture of 6-amino-8-bromo-7-hydroxy-2-methyl chromone (0.005 mole) and appropriate acid (0.005 mole) was dropped into the above. The temperature employed and the duration of the reaction varied with the acid employed. In the case of *p*-toluic acid, *o*-toluic acid and 2-naphthoic acids the reaction mixture was heated first at 150-60° for 2 hours and then at 200-205° for a further period of 4 hours, while in the case of 1-naphthoic acid and pyridine-3-carboxylic acids, the reaction mixture was heated for 3 hours at 170-80° after the initial heating for the same period as above. In the case of *o*-chlorobenzoic acid and coumarin-3-carboxylic acid the reaction mixture was heated for 3 to 4 hours at 180-90° after initial heating, but in the case of 6-bromo-coumarin-3-carboxylic acid the reaction mixture was heated for 3 to 4 hours at 190-200° after initial heating for 2 hours at 150-60°. The mixture was poured over ice-cold water and the resulting solid washed with sodium bicarbonate. Recrystallisation was effected with the appropriate solvent as indicated in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Sl. No.	Pyrano (3,2-f) benzoxazole	m.p. °C	% Yield	Calculated			Found			Solvent
				C	H	N	C	H	N	
1.	2- <i>p</i> -Toluy	250-51	81	58.4	3.2	3.8	58.2	3.2	3.9	Benzene
2.	2- <i>o</i> -Toluy	239-40	95	58.4	3.2	3.8	58.5	3.3	3.9	Benzene
3.	2-(2-Naphthyl)	312-13	95	62.1	3.0	3.5	61.9	3.1	3.6	Benzene
4.	2-(1-Naphthyl)	310-11	94	62.1	3.0	3.5	62.2	3.1	3.6	Benzene
5.	2- <i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	262-63	50	52.3	2.3	3.6	52.5	2.4	3.4	Benzene
6.	2-(3-Coumarinyl)	324-25	89	56.6	2.4	3.3	56.4	2.5	3.2	Aq. Dioxane
7.	2-(6-Bromo-3-coumarinyl)	345-46	92	47.7	1.8	2.8	47.8	1.9	2.9	Aq. Dioxane
8.	2-(3-Pyridyl)	263-64	89	53.8	2.5	7.8	53.6	2.6	7.9	Benzene

Physiological Activity :

All the above compounds have been tested for antibacterial activity using *Staphylococcus aureus* and *E. coli* and pseudo monas aerogenosa. None of the compounds are found to be antibacterial. The same have been tested for antifungal activity using

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